

ISic2945

I.Sicily inscription 2945

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble (Greek?)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2016.05.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance

area of the chiesa del Crocifisso

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo di Archeologia
dell'Universita di Catania, inventory 05/103

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644854

EDCS 70900399

Bibliography

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